

BIAXIAL TESTING OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES USING CRUCIFORM SPECIMENS

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ABSTRACT

An attempt of developing a biaxial testing system for composite laminates was reported in this paper. The testing machine, composed of four hydraulic actuators, enabled independent in-plane biaxial static or fatigue loadings by the load/displacement feed-back control system. The designing cruciform type specimens was studied to obtain desired biaxial stress states in the central area under biaxial loadings. The central region which makes the gauge area is consisted of a reduced section of uniform thickness, and connected by transition surroundings to the full thickness of the arms in order to avoid premature failures in these areas. A two-dimensional finite element method with pre- and post-processors was prepared for designing configurations, stress strain analysis and strength calculation of cruciform specimens. Laminates used in this study are $[0/45/0/-45]_s$ symmetric three-directional laminates of graphite/epoxy, graphite/PEEK and glass/epoxy composites. Preliminary experiments show that the damage extension ratio in the laminate during biaxial fatigue test is much faster under out-of phase loading conditions than that of in-phase loading condition.

KEYWORDS: Loading, biaxial; Laminate; Specimen design; Strength; Test method

1. INTRODUCTION

Laminated plates of fiber reinforced composite have increasingly expanded their application fields in severe service environments, particularly where weight is at a premium. In many practical structures, the composite laminates are subjected to complex loading and the need for experimental data on the strength of these materials under biaxial load has been recognized(1).

Various kinds of specimens have been proposed and used to obtain biaxial-load test data for metallic alloys(2). The most common method of biaxial testing employs the thin-walled tube subjected to combined axial and torsional loads, with internal and external pressures(2-4). However, in some cases such as strength optimized composite plate, in-plane loadings may be better way of biaxial loading(5). Using cruciform specimen is alternative method for biaxial test. It is well known that the cruciform specimens with a reduced-thickness center section and with slotted arms show good uniform stress/strain field in a gauge area, but such designing may not be always applicable to material test of composite laminates. A computer aided designing of cruciform composite specimen was developed to study optimum configurations, which uses two dimensional finite element method with pre- and post-processors.

The anisotropy of composite laminate necessitates the improvement of the conventional biaxial testing machine made up of four hydraulic actuators. A small rigid movement of transverse direction during the test can give unexpected damages to some weak plies in a laminate. It seems to be difficult to control four actuators not to generate imbalance at all by load feed-back

signal only. A double loop feed-back control system was developed to carry out long term fatigue test with high stability and accuracy, and without readjustments of position of specimen.

2. TESTING APPARATUS

The biaxial testing machine consists of four hydraulic actuators of 200 kN tension and compression load capacity each for biaxial static and fatigue tests. These four actuator assemblies make two pairs, and are rigidly mounted in an octagonal box-shaped frame diagonally (Fig.1). Each loading axis is called x- and y-axis in this section. The frame is of heavy duty welded construction, and placed horizontally. Available testing space between pairs of actuators is about 1000 mm maximum.

A load cell and a linear variable differential transformer(LVDT) are installed in each actuator assembly. The end tab areas of cruciform specimen are reinforced by glass/epoxy woven materials, and a pair of steel plates is inserted between each end tab and arm to fasten them with bolts. A close-up view is shown in Fig.2. The components purchased from SCHENK Corporation, Germany, include the four hydraulic actuator assemblies, manifolds, the control console and a hydraulic pump unit.

Fig. 1 Overview of the biaxial testing machine

Fig. 2 Close-up view of the testing machine

To minimize a rigid movement, or shift of the center of the specimen, during biaxial static and fatigue tests, the feedback control system had to be improved. This biaxial testing machine is not only controlled by load signals but also simultaneously by positioning signals. The control system of X1 and X2 actuators which generate the x-axis load in pairs, is shown schematically in Fig.3. For example, a load command signal F_x will be mixed with feedback signals (F_{x1} and F_{x2}). These feedback signals are output signals of transfer function circuit $CX1$ and $CX2$, which are computed from $F1, F2, S1$ and $S2$ signals. The $F1$ and $F2$ are the load cell signals from X1 and X2 actuator, respectively. The $S1$ and $S2$ are the LVDT signals from X1 and X2 actuator, respectively.

The composite laminates are more vulnerable for the drift of the specimen caused by a little load imbalance between four actuators than conventional isotropic materials because the strength along one axis can be much less than the other perpendicular axis. The machine, installed by improved control system, can perform any uni-axial fatigue test, where only one pair of opposing arms of cruciform specimen will be held and loaded and the other pair of arms will be free. The center of a cruciform specimen was almost stationary, less than 0.04 mm drift, during a preliminary fatigue test.

Fig.3 Load/position control system (X-axis)

Fig.4 Mesh generation by the pre-processor and stress distribution display by the post-processor

3. SPECIMEN DESIGN AND STRESS ANALYSIS

A number of different configurations of cruciform specimens have been proposed and investigated for characterizing the material properties under biaxial static and fatigue loads(5-7). The goal of designing specimen is to obtain in the gauge area as uniform stress and strain field as possible and to avoid premature failures in surrounding areas.

Composite materials have the advantage that their mechanical properties can be tailored through fiber orientations, ply thickness ratios, and stacking sequences. This capability gives a designer an additional degree of flexibility to optimize the components as obtaining desired strength or stiffness(8-9). A numerical studies of strength optimization show the laminate which consists of 0,45, and -45 fiber orientations can build up the optimum laminate for a wide range of tension/tension and tension/compression biaxial loading conditions(7-9). In this report, several kinds of symmetric laminate [0/45/0/-45]_s of graphite/epoxy and graphite/PEEK are investigated.

Additional design parameters for composite materials accelerate the use of computers to analyze stress/strain field in gauge areas of specimen and to evaluate feasibility of the configurations. The computer aided specimen design system is strongly required, and under way in several laboratories including ours(5,7).

An attempt was made for designing cruciform specimens using personal computer system. A two dimensional finite element method program is installed as a solver and with pre- and post-processors was prepared for this study. Fig.4 shows a mesh generation result of cruciform specimen by the pre-processor. The effect of shoulder geometry on the stress distribution in gauge areas was studied. As is shown in Fig.5, the A- and B-type specimens were analyzed for graphite/PEEK(APC2) laminate. Both specimens have the same laminate of [45/0/-45/0]_s in central area, and surroundings are added the same materials of [45/-45]_s plies to make a smooth and linear change of thickness to the arms. The central regions consist of a reduced section of uniform thickness, and connected by transition surroundings to the full thickness of the arms. The material properties used in this calculation are taken from the reference 10, and repeated in Table 1.

Table 1 Material properties

Elastic Properties					Strength Properties [MPa]				
MATERIAL	Ex [GPa]	Ey [GPa]	Major Poisson's Ratio	Es [GPa]	Longitudinal		Transverse		Shear
					Tensile	Compressive	Tensile	Compressive	
ALUMINUM (2024-T3)	72	72	0.30	27.7	345	345	345	345	199
Graphite/Epoxy (T300/NS208)	181	10.3	0.28	7.17	1500	1500	40	246	68
Graphite/PEEK (APC2) AS4/PEEK	134	8.9	0.28	5.10	2130	1100	80	200	160

Fig. 5 Specimen geometry to study the effect of shoulder geometry on stress distribution

Fig. 6(a) A-type

Fig. 6(b) B-type

Fig. 6 Stress distribution on the center line along 0 deg direction under uniaxial tension load

Fig. 7(a) A-type

Fig. 7(b) B-type

Fig. 7 Stress distribution on the center line along 90 deg direction under uniaxial tension load

Stress distributions on the center line along 0 degree fiber direction under uniaxial tension were shown in Fig.6(a) for A-type specimen and Fig6(b) for B-type specimen. Similarly, stress distributions on the center line along 90 degree fiber direction were shown in Fig.7(a),(b) respectively. The magnitude and direction of principal stress distributions were represented for B-type specimen in Fig.8. Our limited analyses indicated that the A-type geometry has no significant advantage to B-type.

Fig.8 Principal stress analysis

4. PHASE EFFECT IN BIAxIAL FATIGUE

The effect of loading phase on fatigue damage, mode, and strength was investigated analytically and experimentally. In-plane orthogonal cyclic loads are applied to a cruciform specimen. The wave form of applied stress is assumed to be complete tension/compression sine wave in this study.

The laminate strains and strength ratio of each ply group were calculated under several biaxial loading conditions. The usual assumptions of the symmetric laminated plate theory was used. The laminate is so thin that the laminate strains are equal to ply strains, and therefore they are constant across the laminate thickness. Analytical procedures followed in this report are in Reference 10. The strength ratio(10) based on the quadratic failure criterion was used to estimate the strength of each ply group in the laminate

Figure 9 shows a history of laminate strain e_1 and e_2 along the 1- and 2-axis which coincides with 0 and 90 degree fiber direction in the [45/0/-45/0]_s laminate under uniaxial S1 cyclic stress. The history of 0 and 45/-45 degree ply strength ratio(R00,R45) are analyzed. The strength ratio was decreased to the minimum about R00=2.5 when S1 reached the maximum compressive stress level. Figure 10 to 12 show the results of laminate strain histories and strength ratios when biaxial S1 and S2 stresses were applied. The phase between S1 and S2 made a big differences in the histories of laminate strains and consequently the minimum values of strength ratios during one cycle of biaxial stresses. In the case of in-phase stress condition shown in Fig.10, the strength ratio has the minimum value of about 4.5. But the phase between S1 and S2 reached to the 180 degree (Fig. 12), the strength ratio is decreased to less than 2. However it may not be clear to discuss the fatigue properties directly from the difference of the strength ratios, the acceleration of fatigue damage would be expected from these results.

The effect of biaxial loading phase on fatigue damages was studied experimentally. The biaxial fatigue tests were carried out for the [45/0/-45/0]s glass/epoxy cruciform specimen. It was easier to observe the fatigue damage extension for glass/epoxy materials than carbon fiber composites. The cyclic load level was determined by the previous uniaxial static test results. About 80% of uniaxial static failure stress level of [45/0/-45/0]s laminate and [45/90/-45/90]s laminate were given to each axis as a peak stresses of biaxial fatigue test. Fig.13 shows the experimental results of biaxial fatigue tests. All these biaxial fatigue tests were carried out by the same peak and trough stress level, but different loading phase. As seen in Fig.13, the fatigue damage under in-phase stress condition did not extend so much after 1.6 million cycles (Fig.13-a). However, the fatigue damage accumulated under the 180 degree out-of-phase condition was much severe than that of in-phase test result. The fatigue damage extended over the gauge area after 120 thousand cycles (Fig.13-c).

Fig.9 Variation of strains and strength margin during uniaxial fatigue load

Fig.10 Variation of strains and strength margin during in-phase biaxial fatigue load

Fig.11 Variation of strains and strength margin during out-of-phase(90 deg) biaxial fatigue load

Fig.12 Variation of strains and strength margin during out-of-phase(180 deg) biaxial fatigue load

Phase= 0 deg. N=1,600*1000 cycles

Phase=90 deg. N= 200*1000 cycles

Phase=180 deg. N=120*1000 cycles

Fig.13 Comparison of fatigue damages between in-phase and out-of-phase biaxial loads material: glass/epoxy(Q-G-112-2800)

5. CONCLUSIONS

An attempt was made to decrease the drift of the cruciform specimen during the biaxial testing which is driven by four hydraulic actuators. A computer aided design tool for designing composite cruciform specimens were introduced. The optimum configuration for strength evaluation of composite laminate are still under way of investigations. The importance of biaxial loading phase for estimating fatigue strength was pointed out by analytical and experimental results.

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